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***“Muses are Not Silent”: Ukrainian Music
as a Reflection on the Global Challenges
of Modernity***

■ s ł o w a k l u c z o w e: Russian-Ukrainian war, cultural front,
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The spiritual values associated with Ukrainian self-identification and its aspirations for independence and freedom have always been markers of that country's national spirit. As a consequence, Ukrainian composers in various genres have often been drawn to, and found inspiration in, the historical events shaping the long national struggle of the Ukrainian people for liberation, as well as in the imagery surrounding the nation's spiritual leaders and the leaders of its national uprisings and their asceticism in the name of freedom¹.

The endeavours of the Ukrainian people to protect their freedoms and democratic values have continued unabated in recent history, and especially since the beginning of the 21st century, finding a response in the souls of its composers, using this struggle as a platform for creative reflection in their work.

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The modern information space is saturated with news and discussion of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, which has brought considerable human suffering and destruction, claimed countless victims and plunged the world into darkness, chaos and an abyss of upheaval. The Russian invaders are committing numerous barbaric crimes against humanity in Ukraine with extreme cruelty, resorting to mass rocket attacks to terrorise the civilian population and destroy critical infrastructure. Among other things they have cynically killed artists and destroyed sites of cultural heritage. At the same time, public media highlight the strength of resistance, the fighting spirit of Ukrainians, their unity and belief in victory. An important battle is being fought in this light on the cultural front - the creative output of musicians, writers, artists, representatives of other types of art against the war and in support of Ukraine. Nowadays, many Ukrainian composers, performers, and musicologists have actively joined the cultural and artistic movement to demonstrate to the world the spiritual power of Ukraine, its enormous cultural heritage and the wealth of creative ideas produced by its modern artists.

Various promotional campaigns, charity concerts and other events in support of Ukraine have been organized both within the country and around the world.

For example, the world-famous anonymous graffiti artist Banksy has confirmed his authorship of 7 works in the hottest spots in Ukraine in the first weeks of the war, in particular in Kyiv, Borodianka, Irpin, Hostomel, and Horenka. Banksy's graffiti has appeared on the ruins of buildings destroyed by Russian missile strikes. Visions of Ukraine's peaceful past seemingly captured just moments before the catastrophe highlight the tragedy and brutality of war and remind us of the highest value on earth – the value of human life.

Interest in Ukrainian musical culture has grown remarkably all over the globe. Numerous musical events in support of Ukraine have been organized in Poland this year. The eighth Festival of Ukrainian Music was held in Warsaw on the initiative of Roman Revakovich, a Polish conductor and musical and public figure of Ukrainian origin, featuring both well-known and new works composed by Valentyn Sylvestrov, Leonid Hrabovskiy, Oleksandr Shchetynskiy, Oleh Bezborodko, Bohdana Froliak.

An extensive presentation of modern Ukrainian music, including new avant-garde works by such young Ukrainian composers as Bohdan Sehin, Anna Korsun, and Alla Zahaikevych were performed at the famous international festival "Warsaw Autumn-2022". Bohdana Froliak wrote the music for the theater play *The War That Changed the Rondo*, which was staged at the Warsaw Children's Theater «Hulliver» on September 17². This allegorical fairy-tale about

² See: program of the Międzynarodowy Festiwal Muzyki Współczesnej „Warszawska jesień” 16–24.09.2022, p. 63–66.

the events currently taking place in Ukraine, features lyrical music performed by a string trio, choreography, scenography and acting, which together combine to create a fantastical world in which good triumphs over evil and light over darkness.

Valentyn Sylvestrov's music today constitutes a specific brand of modern Ukrainian culture. It is well known throughout the world and is in demand both as part of individual concert projects and at major European festivals. Sylvestrov's work has become a musical symbol of the solidarity of different peoples and countries, offering a message of support for Ukraine and peace that has reverberated around the world. In March 2022 alone, several of the world's leading musical ensembles gave performances of Sylvestrov's *Prayer for Ukraine* (2014). The symphony orchestra of the German city of Bamberg recorded the piece literally in the first week of the war (on March 7, conducted by Jakub Hrusa) in an orchestral arrangement by Eduard Resatsch. The original choral version was performed, most notably, by the Metropolitan Opera Choir (March 14, 2022, conductor Yannick Nézet-Séguin), the Helsinki Chamber Choir (March 19, 2022, conductor Krista Andere), and the Warsaw Philharmonic Choir (March 25, 2022, conductor Andrzej Borejko).

Audiences heard not only well-known works by Ukrainian composers, but also premieres. Thus, on April 26, 2022, the Warsaw National Philharmonic Hall hosted the world premiere of V. Sylvestrov's new work *Psalm* for a large mixed a cappella choir – 8 variations (attacca) on the theme of the Ukrainian folk song *Oh, from behind the stone mountain*. The piece was written back in 2019, commissioned by the Adam Mickiewicz Institute in Warsaw, but had never been played before an audience. The successful performance of the piece during the war by Poland's leading collective – the National Philharmonic Choir in Warsaw under the direction of Bartosz Michalowski – drew attention to Ukraine and its art in the European cultural community. The work clearly highlights the philosophical problem of the passage of time, the transience of human life, and the futility of vanity. The impetus for the composition came from the Ukrainian folk song *Oh from Behind the Stone Mountain*, the hero of which realized only at the end of his life that he had wasted his young years and that they cannot be recovered. Variational repetition of the same melody with the same text albeit with micro-changes, mainly concerning texture, dynamics, and new timbre combinations of choral groups, reminds the listener of the Lyrny tradition, made use of in his time by Franz Schubert in the vocal cycle *Winter Path*. The romantic and melancholic mood of the work of V. Sylvestrov is created not only by purely musical means. The melody, tonality, and intonation of the language of the text are of great importance. According to the composer, the use of the Ukrainian language affects the character of the music, resonating as it does with such features of his nation's character as dreaminess, poetics,

lyricism, and cordocentricity. On the other hand, today, during these testing times when Ukraine is having to struggle to overcome tragedy, language has a deeply symbolic meaning. As the composer noted, “the very demonstration of the Ukrainian language in public space, in creative events, and concerts confirms that Ukraine as a state exists and has the right to its independence”³.

Another Ukrainian work written and performed during the present war is that of the middle generation composer Zoltan Almashi. This piece for strings is entitled *Requiem. Dedication to Mariupol*. Mariupol suffered extensive destruction and enormous loss of life, and yet, despite this, the defenders of the city courageously fought the enemy. The premiere of Zoltan Almashi’s work took place on June 20-21, 2022 in the city of Graz, Austria. The piece was also performed by the Ukrainian Youth Symphony Orchestra at the “Young. Euro. Classic” international festival in Berlin on August 10, 2022.

The composer himself described the conditions in which this work took shape:

I saw and heard a rocket exploding... The sound was impressive, and the whole night sky turned orange. At that moment I was not thinking about music. There was a moment of numbness and horror⁴.

These feelings are reflected in the music of the work, which is a kind of instrumental lyrical-tragic requiem for the dead.

The sad melody of the viola, in which Ukrainian lyrical and song intonations are felt, is picked up by the orchestra. The music is tonal, comprising three-chord chants, and a romantic shift to the sixth. The timbre of the solo violin in a duet with a cello sounds poignant and nostalgic. The wave-like development leads to the culmination point, in which the tension is increased by the shredding of lengths and a dynamic pumping, leading to a unison on an elastic dotted rhythm. The separate chants and chords of the non-third structure are vertical in form. Against the background of violins in a high register, the alto enters again with his mournful solo, to which individual phrases of violins and double basses are carefully added. In the reprise, the initial element of the Ukrainian lyrical song returns: a beautiful melody is played by violins accompanied by an orchestra. Another solo violin melody appears in the coda, written in the style of a Ukrainian lullaby. Its presentation is characterized by frequent stops, long pauses, and a gradual fading of the sound. In the second passage, a “sub-vocalization” in interval of third occurs, which once again guides the listener to

³ Valentyn Sylvestrov’s interview with the author of the text on 25.04.2022 (from the personal archive of Olena Berehova).

⁴ Zoltán Almászy’s personal Facebook page. Post of 6.10.2022, <https://www.facebook.com/zoltan.al>, accessed: 30.04.2023.

the traditions of Ukrainian folk music. The piece ends with the barely audible sounds of the double bass, which descend lower and lower and seems to dissolve into nothingness.

Oleksandr Shchetynskyi responded to the tragic events of the first months of the war with his chamber work *Lacrimosa*, which was commissioned by the Lviv Organ Hall, where it was premiered on April 17, 2022. The composer wrote this piece in Kyiv in the first weeks of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, when the Ukrainian capital was under constant rocket fire.

Lacrimosa by Oleksandr Shchetynskyi is a mournful song of lament for the people who died in the war and for the country that is suffering from so much destruction. It is also a powerful hymn to the spirit of the Ukrainian people, who have survived many trials in history and are now seeing the blood of their sons being shed in defence of all European civilization.

The work has an unusual instrumental arrangement: violin, oboe, French horn, two trombones and an organ. The composer uses the dramaturgy of timbres as his main compositional technique.

The music commences with trombones and the French horn, each of the performers contributing their own elongated sounds, and a chord is formed. Acoustically, this consonant harmony is a major sextachord, although the work is atonal in general. The oboe joins this chord of the brass section, reciting on one sound or the other. The oboe's narrative intonations give way to a tremulous violin. In a rather long solo episode, the violin "shudders" at various intervals from a second to a quarter. The violin's monologue is continued by the oboe accompanied by the organ, and later the addition of the French horn. Then, the trombones join in, making mostly long, extended sounds. The general character of the music here is static, as if frozen. The functions of the oboe and violin in this composition are complementary: when the oboe stops playing, the violin enters with its trembling lyrical monologues. In the middle part of the composition, spatial stereophonic effects and elements of instrumental theater are used: the wind instrumentalists descend from the stage to the auditorium, playing their parts as they go. The solemn procession of the brass resembles a mournful funeral procession in both its meaning and sound. The brass players stop at the end of the hall and stand opposite the rest of the musicians who remained on stage. For a while, the musical canvas is split into two independent layers. The sound gradually becomes more intense: the violin has fragmentary motifs in the high register and rehearsals on the same sound, the oboe part is also full of «torn» phrases, and the trombones' glissandos resemble air raid warnings. The tense atmosphere is enhanced by a dirty chord cluster in the organ and arpeggiated passages of the brass. In the climax, the organ chords sound like blows, and the violin's «trembling» intensifies.

The brass players return to the stage from the end of the auditorium without stopping playing. In this episode, their movement, together with the increased dynamics of the sound, creates the effect of the fatal approach of a formidable force. In the climactic episode, the repetitive-aleatoric technique is used. A particularly depressing impression is made by the alternation of the chords-strokes of the organ and the tutti unison with the chanting of one sound. In the post-culmination zone, the sound gradually thins out, and the long trombone sounds in the low register return, joined by the oboe. After the final monologue of the violin, the organ plays a melody similar to a Ukrainian folk song. The national character of the episode is emphasized by the harmonic means, in particular by the use of elements of the «dumny» mode (a raised 4th degree in minor). The piece is completed by a group of wind instruments - trombones with horns and oboe, which, as at the beginning of the work, immerse the listener in a meditative state.

Vivid and deeply personalized reflections on the events of the war have been embodied in the works of several Ukrainian women composers. The Odesa-based composer Karmella Tsepkolenko initiated and launched the musical project "Ukrainian Women Artists with Their Guns," which was staged at the 33rd Kyiv Music Fest in September 2022. The project included new chamber cantatas by Ukrainian women composers written during 2022: *Reading History* by Karmella Tsepkolenko for soprano, cello and piano based on the poetry of Oksana Zabuzhko, *Feelings* by Hanna Kopyika for soprano, cello and piano based on the poetry of Lina Kostenko, *With Faith in Ukraine* by Asmati Chibalashvili for soprano, tempo block, cello, piano and video based on the poem by Yulia Dmytrenko-Despotashvili, *My Dear* by Kira Maidenbergh-Todorova for soprano, cello and piano based on the poem by Valeria Zhigalina, and *Signs of Presence* composed by Alla Zagaykevych for soprano, cello and piano and inspired by the verse of Iia Kiva.

The composition *Bucha. Lacrimosa* for violin and symphony orchestra (2022) is a deeply personal reflection of the composer Victoria Poliova on the consequences of Russia's barbaric invasion of Ukraine. The world premiere, performed by the Youth Symphony Orchestra of Ukraine (soloist – Andrii Murza, conductor – Oksana Lyniv), took place at the Beethoven Festival in Bonn on August 29, 2022.

The composer also makes use of the requiem genre. The tragic content of the lacrimosa – the most sorrowful part of the requiem – determines the imagery of the work, particularly in its extreme sections. The main role in the latter is assigned to the poignant melody of the solo violin placed over the rising sounds of the arpeggio and set against the background of a quiet extended string chord. Each subsequent phrase of the soloist's melody rises to a new

height. Disturbing tapping on a wooden box is interspersed with the barely audible background of the strings. In separate passages of the violin solo, the listener can detect the improvisational manner of a traditional Ukrainian folk-instrumental performance. Many semantic connotations arise in connection with the allusion in the work to the famous violin concerto *Winter* from Antonio Vivaldi's *Four Seasons*. This is a symbolic time of the year – when the war began and the tragic events that took place in Bucha, Borodianka and elsewhere shook the whole world with their cynical cruelty. This is nostalgia for a beautiful past that can never return. It conveys a dialogue between eras, each of which is marked by its own tragedies and disasters. In a quite naturalistic way, one episode recalls a violent attack of the enemy, reflected in the loud cacophony of the tutti orchestra with its howling brass section and the monotonous “dull” rhythm of the percussion, which drowns out the fragile “voice” of the violin and strings. It is as if Neo-Expressionist paintings flash before the listener's mind: enemy rockets and bullets fly everywhere and crush everything in its path, conveying visions of damage and destruction in Ukrainian cities, of houses blackened by fire with cracks in walls and holes instead of windows, of human bodies scattered on the streets... The return of the mournful phrases of the violin solo in the reprise section takes place against a changed, indeed distorted background. It is served by a quiet, sonorous cluster of the orchestra, from which the timbres of the clarinet and the flutes stand out, echoing the soloists. The final wary rattling of the wooden box hangs in the air with an eerie uncertainty, a soul-chilling numbness.

Another piece by Victoria Poliova – entitled *Nova* for symphony orchestra (2022), which premiered in Poznań and Warsaw – has a completely different character. The work was written in the first days of the war and is dedicated to the courage of the Ukrainian people. As the composer herself admitted,

this is my contribution to the approaching victory and a low bow to our soldiers. At that time, I didn't know, I couldn't even imagine how terrible the war would be, but it was a premonition⁵.

The piece opens with a duet of solo pipes engaged in an improvisational dialogue, fully in the spirit of the Carpathian trembitas, as if competing in skill and ingenuity. Later, a trombone and a big drum are added to maintain the beat. The competition between the trumpets is interrupted by the hard mechanistic rhythm of the orchestral episode, in which the main role is played by the piano and drums, which are later joined by all the strings. In this heavy aggressive mass, which booms and “stomps” primitively on one sound, the bright timbres

⁵ Victoria Poliova's post on her personal Facebook page dated 11.10.2022, <https://www.facebook.com/victoriavita.poleva>, accessed: 30.04.2023.

of the two trumpets are still conspicuous. The orchestra seems to be trying to crush and destroy the soloists, but as the music develops, an amazing transformation takes place: the dull, mechanistic mass disappears, the sound becomes enlightened and joyfully victorious. The orchestra's second "attack" on the soloists is even more intense and terrifying, with the brass section now the howling and wailing (especially the trombones), but it also somehow quickly "collapses". In the reprise, the clear, uniform rhythm of the snare drums remains, against the background of which once more, as at the beginning, we can hear the pure invincible timbres of the two trumpets in the improvisational manner heard in Carpathian trembitas. At the very end of the piece, the drum beats a clear fraction for a few more beats – and there is complete silence to mark the symbolical end of the war and the much-desired victory of Ukraine.

In this article, attention has been focused on a presentation of modern Ukrainian culture in Europe and the world. This is a culture that had been oppressed, humiliated, outlawed, extinguished for centuries, but which could not be completely destroyed. The works considered in this article embody the personal and creative reflections of Ukrainian artists, magnified by the traumatic experiences of many previous generations. The nation embraced a code of identification based on the immortal tradition of national song and instrumental folklore, which is present in all works in the mediated versions of their authors – as a sign, a symbol of "Ukrainianness". Valentyn Sylvestrov makes active use of the Ukrainian language as a symbol of the nation in his latest choral works and promotes it both in Ukrainian public space and abroad. Individual self-reflexive artistic strategies combine to form a collective strategy of resistance. As if refuting the ancient aphorism of the Roman emperor Marcus Tullius Cicero, "When the cannons speak, the muses are silent." Today the muses are far from silent. The cultural front continues to stir, and Ukraine's voice is heard around the world, as evidenced by the mammoth support provided by many countries for its struggle for the right to exist as an independent state among civilized European nations. Ukraine is not only fighting for its right to exist, it is also fighting barbarity and aggression with fire and sword and defending universal human values – freedom, democracy, and human rights. The music currently being composed by Ukrainian artists is dedicated to these values – the music of resistance, light and hope.

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STRESZCZENIE

„Muzy nie milczą”: muzyka ukraińska jako refleksja nad globalnymi wyzwaniami nowoczesności

Bohaterska starożytność i burzliwe wydarzenia współczesne zawsze stanowiły przedmiot twórczych refleksji. Ukraińscy artyści, jako spadkobiercy kultury starożytnej, w tym podejściu do tworzenia wartości artystycznych pozostają w zgodzie z tradycjami europejskimi. Wiek XXI nie jest wyjątkiem – w różnych częściach świata wybuchają konflikty społeczne i rewolucje, obserwuje się militarną ekspansję zwolenników myślenia kolonialnego, dochodzi do tragicznych wydarzeń związanych z walką całych krajów o prawo do własnej historycznej drogi rozwoju, narodowego samostanowienia i życia.

Ukraińskim kompozytorom impuls twórczy dawały rewolucyjne wydarzenia pierwszych dwóch dekad na Ukrainie, kiedy postępową większość narodu stanęła w obronie prawa do wyboru życia w europejskiej przestrzeni kulturowej i wyznawania europejskich wartości kulturowych. Przedmiotem twórczych refleksji współczesnych ukraińskich kompozytorów stały się: śmierć młodych Ukraińców podczas pokojowych protestów na centralnym placu Ukrainy w Kijowie w roku 2014 oraz konfrontacja społeczeństwa ukraińskiego, odrodzonego po upadku totalitarnego reżimu, z konserwatywnymi siłami będącymi pozostałością poprzedniej epoki. W swoich dziełach kompozytorzy oddają hołd poległym – Bohaterom Niebiańskiej Sotni, którzy oddali życie na Majdanie Niepodległości w Kijowie podczas konfrontacji nieuzbrojonych ludzi z oddziałami sił specjalnych – najemnikami starego rządu.

Tragiczne wydarzenia pierwszych miesięcy roku 2022, związane z rosyjską agresją i prowadzoną na pełną skalę inwazją na Ukrainę, wywołały wśród ukraińskich artystów impulsywną refleksję. Na Ukrainie, a także w innych krajach europejskich, które przyjęły licznych ukraińskich uchodźców, wykształcił

się swoisty front kulturowy – twórcza działalność muzyków, pisarzy, artystów, przedstawicieli innych rodzajów sztuki, skierowana przeciwko wojnie i na rzecz Ukrainy. Moja prezentacja obejmuje najnowsze utwory ukraińskich kompozytorów napisane w czasie wojny, w szczególności *Psalm* na chór a cappella Valentyna Sylvestrova oraz dedykowany Mariupolowi utwór na smyczki Zoltana Almashiego zatytułowany *Miasto Marii*.